

ISic0303

Epitaph for L. Roscius Rufus

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2016.10.14

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

First recorded in 18th century in re-use 'Nel chiostro dei PP. Domenicani sotto titolo di S. Domenico fuori le mura' (Amico)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory 642

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 14.5 cm

Width 67 cm

Depth 2.7-4.8 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Lines 1-2: 22-28 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. · L(ucio) · Roscio · L(uci) · f(ilio) · Quir(ina) · Rufo · pr(aefecto) [coh(ortis)---]
2. equitatae · equo · pub(lico) · adlecto [inVdecurias---]
3. [---]

Apparatus

Text from Korhonen 2004 (supplement to line 2 proposed by Eck)

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491513

EDR 139982

EDCS 21900338

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7019 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 16

Eck, W. 1996. Senatoren und senatorische Grundbesitz auf Sizilien. *Catania antica. Atti del Convegno della societa italiana di studi sull'antichita classica, Catania 1992*. Pisa-Rome. pp. 231-256. At 236-237

Eck, W. 1996. Senatorische familien der kaiserzeit in der provinz Sizilien. *ZPE*. 113: 109-128. At 117

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